

Potential Antineoplastic Agents—III : Synthetic and Pharmacological Studies on Some N-Aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) Thiocarbamides

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A number of compounds belonging to the series N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides have been synthesised by the condensation of corresponding 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazole with different arylisothiocyanates respectively, with the view of testing their antitumor activity. The preliminary pharmacological studies on title compounds have also been carried out.

THERE has been a growing interest, during the last few years, in the synthesis and biological evaluation of compounds containing the N*-N*-S* or O*-N*-S* tridentate ligand system¹⁻⁵ or arylazo grouping^{6,7}. This interest stems mainly from certain interesting biological activities^{8,9}, carcinostatic activities of heterocyclic carboxylaldehyde thiosemicarbazones and the interfering action of 5-arylazopyrimidines in nucleic acid synthesis. Moreover, various Schiff bases from benzaldehyde nitrogen mustards and thiazoleamines have been reported to possess antitumor activities¹⁰⁻¹². As a part of a general study directed towards the development of antineoplastic agents¹³, the above rationale led to an examination of synthesis and biological properties of N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides having N*-N*-S* ligand and arylazo grouping and a modified azomethine linkage. The present communication deals with the synthesis of N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-tolylazothiazolyl)-, N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-anisylazothiazolyl)-, and N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides by the condensation of corresponding 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazoles(II) with appropriate arylisothiocyanates.

The precursor 2-amino-4-p-anisylthiazole(I) was obtained by the condensation of p-methoxyacetophenone with thiourea in presence of iodine¹⁴. The arylazo group at C-5 position was introduced by coupling of various diazonium salts with (I).

On boiling equimolar quantities of arylisothiocyanates¹⁵ and (II) in benzene on a steam bath, high yields of the corresponding N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides (Table I) were obtained. Purification was achieved by recrystallization with DMF-ethanol (1 : 1).

where R'' = 3-Cl, 3-CH₃, 3-OCH₃

and R' = H, 2-CH₃, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃, 2-Cl, 3-Cl, 4-Cl, 2-OC₂H₅.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and a Perkin-Elmer-720 infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were at least of medium intensity. The results of elemental analyses were in good agreement with that of theoretical values.

2-Amino-4-p-anisylthiazole : It was prepared according to the method described in the literature¹⁴.

2-Amino-4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazole¹⁶ : Sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mole) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to a well cooled solution of 3-chloroaniline (2.55 g, 0.02 mole) in 3N-HCl (2.5 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered into a cold suspension of 2-amino-4-p-anisylthiazole (4.12 g, 0.02 mole) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After 2 hrs, the title compound was filtered and washed several times with water. It was recrystallized as red needles from DMF-ethanol (1 : 1) mixture, yield 4.95, (72%), m.p. 184°.

Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClN₄OS : C, 55.73 ; H, 3.77 ; N, 16.25 ; S, 9.28% Found : C, 55.70 ; H, 3.72 ; N, 16.21 ; S, 9.22%. Compounds were shown to be homogeneous (single spot on tlc, silica gel) ; ir, -N=N- (1615 cm⁻¹).

By adopting similar procedure 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-m-tolylazothiazole and 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-m-anisylazothiazole were obtained from diazonium salts of m-toluidine and m-anisidine respectively.

N-Phenyl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamide : A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazole (3.44 g, 0.01 mole) in

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TABLE 1—SYNTHETIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF N-ARYL-N'-2(4-p-ANISYL-5-ARYLAZOTHIAZOLYL) THIOCARBAMIDES AGAINST L-1210 LYMPHOID LEUKEMIA ASCITIC FLUID IMPLANTED INTRAPERITONEALLY IN BDF₁ MICE

Sl. No.	Compounds ^a		Yield %	Melting Point, °C	Molecular Formula	Survivors ^a	T/C ^b , %
	R''	R'					
1.	3-Cl	H	78	222	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	102
2.	"	2-OH ₂	75	239	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	90
3.	"	3-OH ₂	72	253	"	6/6	94
4.	"	4-OH ₂	74	248	"	5/6	104
5.	"	2-OCH ₃	76	271	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	96
6.	"	4-OCH ₃	78	269	"	5/6	103
7.	"	2-Cl	72	284	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	95
8.	"	3-Cl	75	291	"	6/6	98
9.	"	4-Cl	76	209	"	6/6	100
10.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	75	255	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/3	104
11.	3-CH ₃	H	80	230	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	101
12.	"	2-CH ₃	72	210	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	90
13.	"	3-CH ₃	75	224	"	4/6	103
14.	"	4-CH ₃	78	237	"	6/6	100
15.	"	2-OCH ₃	76	246	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	96
16.	"	4-OCH ₃	72	255	"	6/6	102
17.	"	2-Cl	74	242	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	88
18.	"	3-Cl	70	214	"	6/6	104
19.	"	4-Cl	78	239	"	4/6	102
20.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	76	260	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	101
21.	3-OCH ₃	H	80	234	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	3/6	100
22.	"	2-CH ₃	74	285	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	90
23.	"	3-CH ₃	72	275	"	5/6	96
24.	"	4-CH ₃	76	298	"	4/6	105
25.	"	2-OCH ₃	78	283	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	96
26.	"	4-OCH ₃	80	280	"	5/6	105
27.	"	2-Cl	75	268	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5/6	98
28.	"	3-Cl	80	270	"	3/6	94
29.	"	4-Cl	74	278	"	5/6	100
30.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	76	255	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6/6	102

* The analytical results for C, H, N and S in these compounds agreed with ±0.5% of the theoretical values.
 a. All doses for these compounds were 400 mg/kg.
 b. Ratio of mean survival time of test animals (T) to control (C). Mean survival time of control is 30 days.

benzene (15 ml) was refluxed for 6-8 hrs on a steam bath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The crude thiocarbamide thus obtained was crystallized from DMF-ethanol (1 : 1) mixture as deep red needles, yield 3.75 g (78%), m.p. 222°. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₅ClN₂O₂S₂: C, 57.56; H, 3.75; N, 14.59; S, 13.34%. Found: C, 57.50; H, 3.68; N, 14.48; S, 13.28%.

Similarly, other N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides were prepared by the condensation of 2-amino-4-p-anisyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazole with different arylisothiocyanates.

Using similar procedure as above N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-tolylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides and N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-m-anisylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides (Table 1) were also obtained.

These N-aryl-N'-2(4-p-anisyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides were characterized on the basis of their elemental analyses and the presence of characteristic bands N=N(1615 cm⁻¹), NH(3400 cm⁻¹), N=C=S(1520 cm⁻¹) and substituted benzene ring (780 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectra of the compounds.

Biological results: Shown in Table 1 are the data of antitumor activity against L-1210 lymphoid leukemia. From this primary screening data it appears that level of toxicity varied greatly in this group. Compounds Nos. 4, 10, 18, 24 and 26 are somewhat more potent than other members in this series.

References

1. R. W. BROCKMAN, J. R. THOMSON, M. J. BELL and H. E. SKIPPER, *Cancer Res.*, 1956, 16, 167.
2. F. A. FRENCH and B. L. FREEDLANDER, *Cancer Res.*, 1958, 18, 1920.

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3. F. A. FRENCH and B. L. FREDLANDER, *Cancer Res.*, 1960, **20**, 505.
4. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *Cancer Res.*, 1963, **23**, 9.
5. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 585.
6. E. J. MODEST, H. N. SCHLEIN and G. E. FOLEY, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1957, **9**, 68.
7. R. E. HARMON, F. E. DUTTON and H. D. WARREN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 627.
8. D. J. BRAVER, D. P. ROMAN and P. J. STOFFEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 501.
9. R. L. MAYER, P. C. EISMAN and E. A. KONOPKA, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1953, **82**, 769.
10. S. S. SABNIS and K. D. KULRAMI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 447.
11. F. D. POPP and W. KIRSCH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3858.
12. M. G. DHAPALAPUR, S. S. SABNIS and C. V. DELIWALA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 154.
13. H. G. GARG and R. A. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 1122.
14. R. M. DODSON and L. C. KING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242.
15. F. B. DAINS, R. Q. BREWSTER and C. P. OLANDER, *Org. Synth. Coll.*, **1**, 447.
16. H. BEYER and G. WALTER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 1077.